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CONCEPT OF GST

Mrs. Sonu Sharma (Acharya)

M.Com.
V.M.O.U. Kota
&
C.S. Executive Student
ICSI, New Delhi

ABSTRACT

GST the biggest tax reform in the country has kicked in. Although the goods and services get cheaper on account. There will be no hidden taxes and cost involve in doing business. It promotes exports and indirectly increase the country's GDP. Even manufactured goods and services will go down the inflation and benefit the middle. Obligations of tax will be divided equally between the manufacturers and services providers. There has been a drastic increase in the rate of taxes also where the middle class can't afford. BUT, it will be good if a consumer makes the analysis of the applicable rates & then make purchases or consume the services according to his income pattern.

Key Words : Rates, Beneficial

INTRODUCTION

Sixty nine years in the making India rolls out the Goods and Sales Tax(GST) from July 1,2017. Our honourable Prime Minister Narendra Modi led government inaugurated the new indirect tax at the stroke of midnight of June 30 in Parliament.

GST is a landmark step taken by the government of India to boost the GDP and introduced itself as more effective tax regime. In this article, we take a clear a closer look at what is GST and the reasons

Why it is making business and taxes simples.

Firstly, let us know about GST. Goods and Sales Tax is an indirect tax levied in India on the sale of goods and services. It is a vast concept that simplifies that giant tax structure by supporting and enhancing the economic growth of a country. GST aims to streamline the taxation structure in the country and replace a gamut of indirect taxes with a singular to simplify the procedure.

HISTORY

The GST journey began in the year 2000 where a committee was setup to draft GST Law. It took 17 years from then for the law to evolve. In 2017, the GST Bill was passed in the Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha. On 1st July 2017, the GST Law came into force.

COMPONENTS OF GST

Now, a question arise what are its components?

So, in GST there are 3 taxes applicable :

1. **CGST** : Collected by Central Government on an Intra-State Sale
(Eg: Within Rajasthan)
2. **SGST** : Collected by State Government on an Intra-State Sales
(Eg: Within Rajasthan)
3. **IGST** : Collected by Central Government for Inter-State Sale (Eg: Rajasthan to Gujrat)
In most cases, the tax structure under new regime will be as follows:-

Transaction and New Regime:

●Sale within State:

CGST+ SGST

Revenue will be shared equally
b/w Central and State Government

●Sale to another State:

IGST

There will be only one type of tax
in case of inter State Sales. The Central will than share the IGST
Revenue based on destination of goods.

GST is one the biggest economic reform post independence. The system will phase out all indirect taxes and only GST will be applied as an indirect tax. Taxes like excise duty, VAT, service tax, luxury Tax etc. Will go with it.

BEARER OF GST

GST is essentially a consumption tax and is levied at the final consumption point. It is levied on the value addition and provides set offs. As a result, it avoids the cascading effects on tax on tax which increases the tax burden on the end consumer.

G.S.T. SLABS RATES

We already know, as soon as the GST rates were announced a huge wave of curiosity hit across industry and trade bodies. Everyone is evaluating their position as a result of this change. So, here bring an Analysis of these GST rates.

The GST rates are pegged at 0%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. According to the news from the GST Council, the tax structure for common used goods or services are as under:

Taxes Rates :- (as per new and latest data of GST Council Jan. 2018)

*** 0% :** Milk, Egg, Unpacked food grains and paneer, Gur, Handicrafts etc. SERVICES like Education services, all hotels & lodge who carry a tariff below 1000 are exempted etc.

***5% :** Sugar, Tea, Edible oils, Domestic LPG, Life saving Drug, Scientific and technical equipments, Plantation Material. Services like Crude and Petroleum product transportation cabs and radio taxis

***12% :** Sugar Boiled Confectionery, 20 ltr Water bottle, Biodiesel, Bio pesticides, Drip Irrigation System, Old Motor Vehicles(except Medium and large car and SUV), Processed Goods, Ghee, Butter etc. Services like Metro, Monorail Construction Projects, Business class air tickets etc.

***18% :** Hair Oil, toothpaste, Capital goods, Ice cream, Computer and Printers, Used Cars(large and medium cars and SUV), Public transport run by Bio fuel. Services like IT & Telecom Services and Financial services along with branded garments, Theme Park, Water Park, Joy Rides etc.

***28% :** Consumer durables such as AC and fridge, Luxury and Sin items like BMW aerated drinks. Services like Race clubs and gambling, 5 Star Hotels, Entertainment and Cinema. Last but not the least, reduces 3% to .25% on Diamond and other expensive stones.

BENEFICIAL FOR CONSUMERS:

The main reason behind this was to consolidate all indirect taxes into one, thus making it "*ONE NATION, ONE TAX*".

G.S.T. is win-win situation for the entire country.

There were several loopholes & limitations in previous indirect tax regime which compelled the Govt.

GST is a revolutionary step in the indirect taxing regime. It boost to the Indian economy in the long run. GST is beneficiary to common people like:

- GST helps to eliminate "tax on tax" or cascading impact of tax, thus bringing down the overall cost of goods.
- GST ushers in greater transparency for consumers.
- It benefits manufactures too. Instead of liaising with multiple tax authorities, the manufacture gets to deal with a single entity- the GST network.
- Lower the burden on the common man i.e. public will have to shed less money to buy the same products that were costly earlier.
- A big advantage of the GST that is being swept under the carpet in the blanket rate comparisons is the seamless input tax credit.
- GST is a reform move where one can be fairly sure that short-term pain will lead to long -term gains.
- Transportation cost could also fall down to reductions in long and winding queues at border checkpoints within and between the States. Thus will reduce operational cost and will benefit companies.
- GST could also boost exports by making Indian goods competitive in global markets. Exports will be treated as zero rated supplies.
- GST will deliver significant benefits by improved taxation efficiency and ease of doing business and will convert India into one common market, Finance Minister ArunJaitley has said.

Every taxpayer is provided GSTIN unique GSTIN. It is the unique number each taxpayer will receive once they have registered on the common portal. It is based on a taxpayer's PAN.

CONCLUSION

Thus, GST the biggest tax reform in the country has kicked in. Although the goods and services get cheaper on account. There will be no hidden taxes and cost involve doing business. It promotes exports and indirectly increase the country's GDP. Even manufactured goods and services will go down the inflation and benefit the middle. Obligations of tax will be divided equally between the manufacturers and services providers.

There has been a drastic increase in the rate of taxes also where the middle class can't afford. BUT, it will be good if a consumer makes the analysis of the applicable rates & then make purchases or consume the services according to his income pattern.

REFERENCES

- *"All your queries on GST answered". *The Hindu*. Retrieved 2017-06-30.
- *"GST: Cars, durables face 28% rate; luxury vehicles to attract 15% cess", *Business Standard*, 18 May 2017
- *International journal of Education and Applied sciences research
- *International journal of Marketing and financial management
- *International research journal of commerce , arts and science
- *www.thehindu.com
- * www.elocomaindia.com
- * www.clear-tax.in
- * www.gstindiaexpert.com
- * www.indianexpress.com
- * www.wikipedia.org
- * www.jaagore.com
- * www.legodesk.com